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DRAFT

1 EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

On September 4, 2014, COSMIC held its fourth stakeholder engagement workshop in Istanbul, Turkey. The workshop aimed to provide a multi-disciplinary space for different stakeholders to share their respective research and provide feedback to the findings from the deliverables in Work Package 4 of the COSMIC project.

The workshop had 4 sessions organized thematically with respect to utilization of media and ICTs in citizen involvement in emergency response and preparedness. Each session contained a number of presentations from COSMIC consortium partners and stakeholders from other projects/institutions and a discussion session that helped get feedback about the COSMIC findings and incorporate findings from COSMIC project with other findings. The discussions at this workshop highlighted several key points and conclusions. In addition to these four sessions, there were two keynote speeches given respectively by Patrick Meier, whose speech focused on technologies that can be used to engage the public in emergency response and Farida Vis, whose speech focused on, information verification in social media, a recurring problem that COSMIC has also focused on.

The workshop has underlined the potential that citizen participation through social media may play in alerting response authorities and enhancing situational awareness. Yet, the output of the workshop also suggests that the sheer volume of information and the pace with which misinformation may spread via social media represent two challenges that have to be dealt with in order to optimally benefit from citizen involvement in emergency response. Combining crowdsourcing and machine learning as well as increasing the availability of local volunteers who can translate, filter and verify information stood out among the solutions that may help address these challenges.

With respect to how response organizations utilize social media to outreach to and collaborate with citizens, both the findings presented by COSMIC and feedback from workshop participants indicate that while response organizations are increasingly more receptive to the idea of utilizing social media to involve citizens, structures of large organizations and lack of trust continue to be important obstacles.

The feedback has now been analysed by project partners and will be taken into consideration for the development of the guidelines for citizens, government authorities, first responders and industry, for identifying areas of research that needs further attention in use of ICTs in emergency situations, and to make revisions to the reports prepared for WP4.

The present document reports on this workshop for WP4, Task 4.3.

2 INTRODUCTION

The preparation of the workshops started in September 2013 and KU coordinated the organization process, using two consortium meetings to define the agenda, agree on speakers and allocate the tasks.

In order to maximise the diversity of countries represented in the workshop, it was decided that the workshop would be held in English, and that simultaneous translation service would be provided between English-Turkish and Turkish-English. This was considered as an essential factor to facilitate the inputs and contributions of the participants.

3 WORKSHOP IN TURKEY

3.1 WORKSHOP SUMMARY

3.1.1 Preparation and Promotion

The workshop in Turkey was held on September 4th 2014 at the Koç University Research Center for Anatolian Civilizations, Istanbul and was attended by 48 participants including the COSMIC project members and two keynote speakers.

Figure 1 - Research Center for Anatolian Civilizations, located in Beyoğlu Istanbul

For the organization of the workshop, we utilized two methods of soliciting presenters. First, on August 2013, a public call for papers was distributed in online academic networks such as the European Communication Research and Education Association (ECREA) and Media, Communication and Cultural Studies Association (MECCSA) (See ANNEX A). Second, a

shortlist of key practitioners and researchers were identified by partners and were then invited for the workshop.

In response to the public call for papers, 22 papers were submitted which were subjected to a blind review by the Koç University team. 8 of the submitted papers were accepted and after two cancellations, 6 of the accepted papers were presented during the workshop. The invited participants were as follows:

- Patrick Meier, iRevolution
- Farida Vis, University of Sheffield
- Caroline Rizza, Télécom ParisTech
- Anja Hoog Antink, National Police of the Netherlands
- Çağlar Akgüngör, AKUT
- Pat Mendonca, NATO, Civil Emergency Planning Committee

The promotion of the workshop was done through various media. First, a separate subpage under the COSMIC website was created to inform users about the workshop and updates (Figure 2). Second, social media and targeted e-mails were used to invite key stakeholders to the workshop. Figure 3 (left) shows the e-mail invite (in Turkish) sent to 600 potential stakeholders from Turkey. Figure 3 (right) shows the most recent announcements regarding the workshop from COSMIC Twitter page. Finally, in addition to online media, the workshop was promoted via posters and fliers distributed in various University campuses in Istanbul (Figure 4). The invitations & reminders were further forwarded to a wide network of PSCE via ICONCONTACT (Figure 5)

Figure 2 - Webpage of the COSMIC Istanbul Workshop

Figure 3 - E-invite in Turkish (left), Updates on COSMIC Twitter account (right)

Figure 4 - Conference posters in English (left) and in Turkish (right)

Figure 5: Call for papers sent via ICONTACT

As a result of the promotion efforts, 73 potential participants registered online for the workshop. Out of the 73 registrations, 48 actually participated in the workshop. Table below compares the 4 COSMIC workshops organized so far in terms of stakeholder category participation. In general, a good balance of distribution of stakeholders was achieved between industry, government and civil society organizations. However, as with the other stakeholder engagement workshops organized by COSMIC, mass media showed much less interest than other stakeholders. Table 2 lists the full list of participants, their respective countries and institutions.

Table 1 - Stakeholder participation by category in COSMIC workshops

Stakeholder category	Greece	Netherlands	Sweden	Turkey
Industry	1	7	9	11
Government	2	33	12	6
Civil society organizations	1	1	2	14
Academia	1	2	9	16
Media	0	3	0	1

3.1.2 Overview of Schedule & Sessions

The final schedule of the workshop is available in ANNEX B. The workshop focused on the discussion of issues related to use of new media technologies and social media by citizens/to involve citizens during emergencies and for emergency preparedness.

To open the workshop, the coordinator of the project, Ioannis Kotsiopoulos (ED), started with a presentation about the COSMIC project in general. He explained the structure of the project, its goals and partnership, and presented a brief overview of the first results and the “agenda” for the second year of the project.

Next, two keynote speeches were delivered by Patrick Meier from iRevolution and Farida Vis, The University of Sheffield. The keynote speakers focused on two issues that were of high importance for the WP4. First, Patrick Meier spoke about new applications and methods that are being used to fuse crowdsourcing using manual human labour and technologies that can augment the manual human labour. He also described some of the organizational challenges that need to be addressed for better utilization of social media and other technologies to involve the public in emergency preparedness and response. Second, Farida Vis discussed issues related to information verification in online contexts. Her speech also focused on up and coming techniques in verification of imagery during crises.

There were four sessions in the workshop. Each addressed a different theme with respect to public’s engagement in emergency preparation and response, particularly focusing on use of communication technologies.

The first session focused on citizen journalism/reporting. The first paper, by Glenda Cooper, discussed utilization of citizen reporting by mass media. The second presentation, by Paola Costa Cornejo and Caroline Rizza used the Penguins’ Revolution in Chile as a case study of the dual use and on the idea of democratization through communication technologies. Particularly, this presentation discussed the role that citizen journalism may play to challenge misinformation disseminated via mass media. In the last presentation of the session, Lemi Baruh and Haluk Mert Bal focused on the content of citizen reporting. This analysis provided evidence suggesting that while citizen reporting may increase the voice allocated to citizens as stakeholders, the forms of reporting and sense making by citizen journalism often parallels that of mainstream media.

The second session focused on opportunities and threats that arise from the utilization of public generated information. In the first presentation of the session, Rémy Bossu summarized how information shared by the public online can be utilized to estimate the magnitude and potential impact of an earthquake. In the second presentation, Gregory Asmolov discusses how ICTs are used by citizens to define a framework of response to a disaster. In the third presentation, Zeynep Günel and Gökçe Karaoğlu discuss the role ICTs play in the formation and dissolution of loose networks of social activists during and in the aftermath of political crises. The final presentation, by Hayley Watson and Lemi Baruh

focuses on ethical concerns that arise from public's involvement in collection and dissemination of information during emergencies and crises.

The third session had two papers focusing on how response organizations (including civil organizations like AKUT and HRT as well as police authorities) utilize social media to engage citizens in emergency preparedness and response. The first presentation, by Salvatore Scifo, Yusuf Salman and Alex Papadimitriou, engaged in a comparative analysis of the different communication technologies that response organizations and government authorities utilized to engage citizens in emergency preparedness and response. In the second presentation, Anja Hoog Antink discussed how a new generation of officers in the police force in Netherlands could help better deploy social media to outreach to citizens. She also discussed an organizational obstacles that impede this potential.

The fourth session aimed to provide additional findings regarding how different communication means are used by stakeholders to engage the public and propose a set of guidelines regarding the utilization of communication technologies to engage the public. In the first presentation, Aziz Şasa focused on alternative means of communications which are independent of public communication infrastructures that may be damaged or overloaded during emergencies. In the second presentation, Çağlar Akgüngör outlines how undue attention from media may become counterproductive in terms of relationship between response organizations, public and other authorities. The third presentation, by Pat Mendonca, provided a set of principles that can be used by large organizations while engaging with public. Finally, the presentation by Ira Helsloot and Astrid Scholtens summarized a preliminary version of the COSMIC guidelines for citizen engagement via communication technologies.

3.2 DISCUSSION OUTCOMES

In line with the aim of WP4, which focuses on citizen involvement and utilization of new communication technologies during emergencies and crises, the main focus of the discussion points during the workshop were:

- Opportunities presented by crowd-sourced information
- Information overflow as a problem of crowd-sourced information
- Information reliability and verification
- Ethical issues related to privacy and confidentiality
- Citizen journalism during emergencies
- Response organizations' relationship with citizens

The main discussion outcomes are summarized below:

- Participants in the workshop have provided additional examples to how citizen sourced information may contribute to emergency response in various ways. For example, Citizen Seismology was shown as an example of social media traffic, can be used to estimate the location and predict the effects of an earthquake before response teams arrive on the scene.

- Similarly, workshop participants have discussed how citizen sourced classification of events and actions (folksonomy) during an emergency may supplement intelligence gathered through top-down taxonomies.
- At the same time, it was also noted that the contribution of crowd-sourced information may, at least partly, be determined by the stage of the emergency and the related purposes for which social media is used. For example, it has been noted by several participants that while online communication tools may be very effective in “alerting” to an event, as the emergency response and/or crisis progresses too much noise may reduce the usefulness of information generated by public online.
- Given the problem of noise, managing information overflow was discussed as a key component for increasing the effective utilization of crowd-sourced information. The discussion highlighted that up and coming applications such as Zooniverse, Zoomanitarrians, Humanitarian UAV Network combine human computing (volunteers filtering information) and machine learning to manage the overflow of information.
- Credibility of information is also crucial but it takes time to analyse the flow of information. Different projects and application already exist to rate the credibility of messages or photos and provide real-time performance of credibility score. Crisis managers will need information on the trustworthiness of the information and credibility of resources used. Examples of tools: twitcident.com; tweetcred.
- The utility of such applications is frequently limited by the language barrier. Namely, while machine learning approaches and natural language processing capabilities are increasingly available in English and other widely used languages, getting information from languages used locally in emergency effected areas still presents a challenge. The workshop participants have proposed different solutions to this problem, most significantly, the development of local charters of global humanitarian networks and promotion of what the workshop participants have called as “activist translators” who can mediate between local languages and English as a language that is more commonly used by applications utilizing natural language processing capabilities.
- A related solution that has been proposed by stakeholders has been the use of a combination of social media and conventional telecommunication methods for information filtering and sharing. For example, one group of stakeholders from Turkey mentioned how they used a group of volunteers to verify information online and then use two-way radio to communicate the information to response organizations and authorities.
- Another important dimension of the discussions regarding information dissemination and verification pertains to the role that citizens play as reporters/witnesses during emergencies and crisis.
- Participants frequently argued that despite a promise of trickling down of reporting, citizen reporters are similar to mass media in terms of writing and dissemination information. Some participants have alluded to the saturation of mass media as a source of information that dominates even the “citizen” way of sense-making. Researchers indicated that they have observed that alternative ways of sense-making about an emergency like Katrina, may become possible only after a considerable time passes and mainstream media coverage becomes less saturated.

- Another point that was discussed by various stakeholders was the “appropriateness” of the citizen journalism frame as a way to study the reporting activities of citizens. Namely, as also has been noted in WP4, stakeholders indicated that a considerable proportion of the citizens who end up reporting about an emergency are not “citizen journalist” but rather are “accidental reporters” who are equipped with recording devices (i.e., mobile phones) and who happen to be at the right place at the right time.
- The discussions suggest that the distinction between “citizen journalist” and accidental reporter” has important implications with respect to developing guidelines that can be used for production and dissemination of verifiable information in social media. First, dissemination of such guidelines need to be much wider than it is currently assumed to be. Second, as also discussed in WP4, the role that “professional journalists” need to play as gatekeepers of information disseminated online also has been emphasized by stakeholders. Third, stakeholders commented that part of the strategy in reducing the diffusion of misinformation should target the end users. Accordingly, this strategy could focus on increasing the widespread availability of information verification tools and increasing public’s awareness of methods to verify information.
- In line with the findings summarized in WP4, another problem that has been repeatedly discussed by stakeholders concerns privacy issues raised by the utilization of social media to disseminate information about events that transpire during emergencies. With respect to privacy and confidentiality issues, stakeholders proposed the utilization of frameworks such as “privacy by design” and respect of “contextual integrity” to develop rules of conduct. Privacy by design principle, for example, argues that rather than adding it as a post-hoc solution, privacy protection should be planned in advance while designing systems. The concept of “contextual integrity” underlines the notion that data flows about individuals are governed by norms and expectations. These norms and expectations vary depending on a number of factors such as the type of information, actors involved, and the setting. The key to safeguarding individual privacy is protection of the contextual integrity of information, which collapses when information meant to be used in one context is used in another.
- With respect to how organizations utilize social media to engage the public, the comments from stakeholders underlined three important points. First, several stakeholders have given examples to how they started using crowd-sourcing to aid in their emergency response activities. For example, AKUT, an emergency response organization from Turkey, which was discussed in detail in WP4, has reported that since the Van Earthquake, they have been using a team of volunteers to monitor social media. Reportedly, AKUT also was able to identify the location of and rescue an earthquake victim from his/her (identity not given) tweets. Second, there seems to be a generational difference with respect to the extent to which members of response organizations are willing to use social media to interact with public. Third, organizational structures and policies continue to be one of the main obstacles against the wider adoption of social media by such organization.

3.3 AFTER THE WORKSHOP

Following the successful workshop, PSCE uploaded all presentations on COSMIC website. Both PSCE and the project website were updated. This was announced to all relevant contacts via dedicated news item as well as via social media channels. Any new contact will be added

to the contact list in order to ensure continuous interactive dialogue in further stages of the project.

Presentations:

- COSMIC project (EN) - PPT
 - COSMIC project (GR) - PPT
 - State of the art of new communication media - PPT
 - Case studies on the use of new media in crisis situations - PPT
 - Presentation of the Athena Project - PPT
 - Strategic use of emerging communication technologies for crisis stakeholders - PPT
 - Threats and challenges related to the use of social media in crisis management - PPT
 - Crises, new media ethics and the consequences of citizens' involvement - PPT
 - Developing the stakeholders engagement - PPT
- COSMIC Istanbul - Ira Helsloot - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Lemi Baruh and Mert Bal - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Alex Papadimitriou, Salvatore Scifo and Yusuf Salman - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Hayley Watson and Lemi Baruh - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Ioannis Kotsiopoulos - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Paola Costa Cornejo and Caroline Rizza - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Pat Mendonca and Andrew Wright - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Remy Bossu - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Anja Hoog - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Aziz Sasa - PPT
 - COSMIC Istanbul - Caglar Gungor - PPT

Figure 6 Workshop presentations uploaded on the COSMIC website

3.4 LIST OF PARTICIPANTS

Table 2 provides the list of participants for the COSMIC Istanbul workshop.

Table 2 - List of participants

Name	Last Name	Affiliation	Country
Çağlar	Akgüngör	AKUT Institute of Training and Research	Turkey
Nevin	Algül	Marmara University İletişim Fakültesi	Turkey
Gregory	Asmolov	London School of Economics and Political Science	United Kingdom
Mert	Bal	Koç University	Turkey
Marie-Christine	Bannamour	PSCE AISBL	Belgium
Lemi	Baruh	Koç University	Turkey
Manfred	Blaha	PSCE AISBL	Belgium
Alev	Bulut	Çeviri Derneği, Afette Rehber Çevirmenlik İnsiyatifi	Turkey
Glenda	Cooper	Centre for Law, Justice and Journalism, CU London	United Kingdom
Chris	Dekkers	Safety Region South Holland South	Netherlands
Vedat	Demir	Istanbul University	Turkey
Ali	Eker	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Proje Ajansı	Turkey
Evren	Emek	Sivil Toplum Afet Platformu	Turkey
Gürhan	Ertür	Açık Radyo	Turkey
Stella	Gkika	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Proje Ajansı	Turkey
Burcu	Gökçay	Şişli Belediyesi	Turkey
Matt	Gould	NSW Rural Fire Service	Australia
Özdemir	Günday	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Proje Ajansı	Turkey
Zeynep	Günel	Koç University	Turkey
Ira	Helsloot	Crisislab	Netherlands
Anja	Hoog Antink	National Police of the Netherlands	Netherlands
Akın	Ilıca	Istanbul AFAD	Turkey
Tunç	Karaçay	IDEMA Danışmanlık	Turkey
Gökçe	Karaoğlu	Koç University	Turkey
Ioannis	Kotsiopoulos	European Dynamics	Greece
Burak	Küçük	Maltepe University	Turkey
Patrick	Meier	iRevolution	United States
Pat	Mendonca	North Atlantic Treaty Organization	United States
Sevil	Nazlı	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Projeler Ajansı	Turkey

Name	Last Name	Affiliation	Country
Didem Özgür	Özden	Sivil Toplum Afet Platformu	Turkey
Stavros	Paschalidis	Hellenic Rescue Team	Greece
Nicos	Priporus	Hellenic Rescue Team	Greece
Bossu	Rémy	European-Mediterranean Seismological Centre	France
Caroline	Rizza	Télécom ParisTech - Institut Mines-Télécom	France
Yusuf	Salman	Koç University	Turkey
Aziz	Şasa	TRAC Türkiye Radyo Amatörleri Cemiyeti	Turkey
Astrid	Scholtens	Crisislab	Netherlands
Salvatore	Scifo	Koç University	Turkey
Sevcan	Süğüt	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Proje Ajansı	Turkey
Kayıhan	Turgutoğlu	Beyaz Gemi Sosyal Proje Ajansı	Turkey
Nicolaas	van Os	Veiligheidsregio Zuid-Holland Zuid	Netherlands
Farida	Vis	University of Sheffield	United Kingdom
Iosif	Vourchachis	Hellenic Rescue Team	Greece
Kush	Wadhwa	Trilateral Research & Consulting	United Kingdom
Hayley	Watson	Trilateral Research & Consulting	United Kingdom
Tina	Worley	North Atlantic Treaty Organization	United States
Mevlit	Yurtseven	Uluslararası Doktorlar Derneği	Turkey
Gizem	Zorludemir	University of Erlangen-Nuremberg (FAU)	Germany

4 ANNEX A WORKSHOP IN TURKEY: CALL FOR PAPERS

Involving Citizens in Emergency Preparedness and Response

International Conference

Location: Koç University Research Center for Anatolian Civilizations, Istanbul

Date: September 4, 2014; Thursday

New communication technologies play an increasingly important role during emergencies and crises, such as natural and man made disasters and political crises. Particularly social media can potentially enable citizens to more quickly share information, assist response and recovery in emergencies, and mobilize for action in political crises.

This conference will examine the role of citizens as first responders, social activists, and citizen journalists at times of emergencies and crises and will focus on practical, theoretical, and ethical issues related to citizen participation in emergency/crisis response/communication. The conference will result in a set of guidelines for citizens, government authorities, first responders and industry for the most effective use of ICTs to aid citizen security during crises.

Possible topics include, but are not limited to:

- The role that conventional media and social media may play in recruitment and training of emergency response volunteers
- Community involvement in emergency response planning
- Social activism, mobilization, and social media
- Citizen journalism and social media (e.g., reporting processes, threats to citizen journalists involved in coverage of emergencies, information verification)

Selected papers from the conference will be published in the *Interactions: Studies in Communication & Culture* journal (published by Intellect Books).

Submission Information:

Full Papers: Submit a 500 word maximum proposal and a short author biography to Mr. Mert Bal hbal13@ku.edu.tr

PechaKucha Poster Papers: Submit a 250 word maximum proposal and a short author biography to Mr. Mert Bal hbal13@ku.edu.tr

Key Dates:

- Deadline for Submissions: February 14, 2014
- Announcement of Decisions Regarding the Submissions: March 15, 2014
- Announcement of the Workshop Programme: May 15, 2014
- Registration (free): May 15, 2014 – July 15, 2014
- Submission of Full Paper (format to be announced later): August 15, 2014

5 ANNEX B WORKSHOP IN TURKEY: AGENDA

Involving Citizens in Emergency Preparedness and Response

Koç University, Research Center for Anatolian Civilizations, Istanbul

September 4, 2014

08:00 - 08:30 Workshop Registration and Coffee Service

08:30 - 08:45 Introduction to the COSMIC Project - Ioannis Kotsiopoulos

08:45 - 10:15 Opening Speakers

Patrick Meier, iRevolution

Farida Vis, The University of Sheffield

10:30 - 11:45 Citizen Reporting

Hurricanes and hashtags: How the media and NGOs treat citizens' voices online in humanitarian emergencies
Glenda Cooper, Centre for Law, Justice and Journalism, City University London

Social and ethical considerations about the use of social media during a political crisis: The case of the Penguins' Revolution in Chile

Paola Costa Cornejo and Caroline Rizza, Télécom ParisTech

Content of citizen reporting during emergencies

Lemi Baruh and Haluk Mert Bal, Koç University

11:45 - 12:00 Coffee Service

12:00 - 13:30 Citizen Sourced Information and Communication

Towards citizen Seismology

Rémy Bossu, Euro-Med Seismological Centre

Generative activity: Crowdsourcing and the folksonomy of emergency response

Gregory Asmolov, London School of Economics and Political Science

Ethical considerations of citizens' use of ICTs in emergency response

Hayley Watson, Trilateral Research & Consulting and Lemi Baruh, Koç University

Bridging online and offline action: Communication networks and activism

Zeynep Günel and Gökçe Karaoğlu, Koç University

13:30 - 14:30 Lunch Service

14:30 - 15:45 Involving the Public in Emergency Communication I

Engaging citizens in emergency preparedness and response: Comparative analysis of response organizations in Turkey, Italy, Greece

Salvatore Scifo, Yusuf Salman, Koç University and Alex Papadimitriou, Hellenic Rescue Team

Social media & the police: An investigation into the needs of Generation Einstein for the deployment of social media by the police in the Netherlands

Anja Hoog Antink, National Police of the Netherlands

15:45 - 16:00 Coffee Service

16:00 - 17:30 Involving the Public in Emergency Communication II

Networking of alternative communication tools with public communication infrastructures in emergencies by volunteers

Aziz Sasa, TRAC HQ

Citizen engagement and disaster response: Case of AKUT

Çağlar Akgüngör, AKUT

Guidelines for public information during a crisis

Pat Mendonca, NATO, Civil Emergency Planning Committee

And what does it all amount to? Discussing first ideas for guidelines for the use of social media in crisis

Ira Helsloot and Astrid Scholtens, Crisis Lab